

ICAM1

CXCL3

NFKBID

MAP3K14

ST7-AS1

ALMS1-IT1

N4BP3

DFFBP1

PKDCC

AMH

CCDC141

GBP5

AC023310.4

AC136604.2

HSPA7

C15orf48

ITGAM

SORBS2

AP000944.5